

EFFECT OF FOREIGN IMPURITIES ON FIBER AND LINT QUALITY IN COTTON GINS.

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Abstract : Cotton cleaning in factories demonize during of fiber separated seeds big sand , wood , metal fragments and small stones with it gets dirty . From this except empty and not done seeds will be Especially in the car typed of cotton in the seed a lot impurities occurs . That's why the seed from linter before he thoroughly is cleaned . And this of lint dirtiness reduces In the article a stranger of mixtures fiber and fluffy to quality effect about word held

Key words : Fiber , fluffy , light industry , export , linter, construction , limt , regenerators .

INTRODUCTION.

The fiber is complete separated seeds cleaning technological in process of equipment the work productivity , product quality increase on the issue of b researchers by analyses take but this matter is complete own solution did not find It is known linter from the process after fluffy in the composition dirty mixtures the amount of k o 'pb die from it removable of products quality to decrease take will come . Fluff cleaning process done increase complicated and cleaning that the efficiency is low account taking and lintering from the process before the seed cleaning through work being released fluffy contained dirty mixtures the amount reduce can Demonization from the process after the seed according to cleaning b enough scientific studies take did not go or attention not received aspects there is

The world in the market products sell big opportunities to give with work together issuer undertake in charge task , that is work being released products competitiveness also imposes the provision . Cotton cleaning , textile and light industry enterprises by work being released cotton fiber and his products quality indicators high to be , the world standards requirements answer to give their in the world buyer of being main is a factor .

It is known cotton fiber - textile and light industry of products main raw material is considered That's why also in Uzbekistan cotton fiber work to issue big importance is given With that together , abroad hand for sale cotton fiber and his products our country currency of income main from sources is considered

In our republic work being released cotton fiber of the world the majority countries , that's it including USA, Greece , Russia , England , South Korea , Italy , Germany , Holland , Japan and to others is also exported .

Currently , in our country being prepared cotton fiber from 2020 100% from us again work ready the product export to do issue dolzab is considered The world in the market fiber whiteness , contamination level and especially the microneur to the indicator separately attention is given Microneur indicator from 4.8 -4.9 high if fiber rough is considered and the world in the market competition ca n't Rough fiber purchase the price will be low . Cotton to the fiber price in defining main and acceptable indicator 23.5 -26.4 gk / tex his comparison interruption power is considered

So if so , go ahead good quality to be not only breeder scientists and to the grower , perhaps him again working of enterprises working right organization and standard requirements action to do depends will be That is , quality fiber work in release his natural quality indicators (length , color , thickness , ripening done and) with together , cotton again at work right technological process installation , then used of machines technical status separately important have Quality repaired , working of organs movement modes , technological intermediate distances right installed and improved configured of machines in technology use , good quality product work to issue guarantee to say that it gives can

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS.

Lint good quality to be sow good to be cleaned depends . That's why for linter from the process before the seed to clean big importance to give need In ginning , with seeds cotton contained of impurities one part fiber with joined and left part while to the seed mixed up without of the linter the work to his camera falls From the devil coming out seed in the composition big sand , fine pebbles and by accident by joining the rest metal parts to be can From this except , seed in the composition empty and cooked don't be seeds that it was for these are technological in progress car parts effect with crushed and divided goes and Saw to the teeth stuck the rest to lint mixed up without separate out , the lint pollutes . Some cases to the seed fiber full not separated alone seeded the addition of cotton can

The seed cleaning as a result linter process improves , lint quality is fiber a waste won't be and seed long time quality even when stored unbroken , him next performance , that is sorting , medication and oil in the industry to use it becomes easier .

Lint is used cellulose industry and that's it such as another industry in his networks quality high to be Demand will be done .

Lintering from the process after lint cleaning current not done and on this issue near of times starting from scientific check works take going due to now the seed from linter before to clean main attention is given .

That's why for today's in the day seed cleaning technique and technology improvement , fiber , fluff , seed fruitful and good quality exit provide about scientific research done increase to the goal is appropriate .

Cotton contained lie down of mixtures one part demonize in the process to fiber by joining goes , one part while seeds to the composition join them pollutes . From demon next seeds in the composition sand , fine dirt , leaves , metal the division of bodies can From this except , seeded in mass of seeds good undeveloped , ripe immature small ones even occurs . These are different processes on time crushed and crushed and fluffy and seed of dirtiness to increase take will come . From this except seeds in the composition fiber is complete separate not received seeds even become available and them sorted get through fiber exit increase opportunity is created . Demonized hairy seeds again work for next technological to the process transfer quality indicators importance account received without , from this except last in years work to issue new specific physical mechanic to properties have cotton varieties current being done attention take work release conditions hairy seeds fraction content o ' study in order to studies was held . Cotton raw materials cultivation , residue hairy from seed fiber separation (linterlash) , quality fiber work release and delivered to give people of the farm basically is considered Cotton initial at work residual hairy from seed fiber separation , seed enough level that it is not cleaned is showing . For this reason of linters foreign technique and technologies deep learning and achievements and experiences based on In our republic

there is linters improvement and their efficiency increase current from tasks one being is coming Cotton in linting technique and technology including improvement high good quality fluffy get main is one of the problems . That's why for fluffy in getting the seed complete separate good quality fluffy get the quality of the linter increase according to to be done scientific research separately important have is happening Demonization from the process after seed on the surface certain amount basically short has been fiber remains . These fibers it is said to be fluffy . Fluffy , as you know seed to " scrape " from the surface the way with separate is taken . Cut off receiver technological the machine is called a linter . Fluffy length from 6 mm to 26 mm will be if fiber length from 6 mm short if , then this it is called hair . Feather while special hair separator - delinter in their cars separate is taken .

CONCLUSION

That's it to emphasize that 's all in construction regenerators execution need has been work full doesn't do it . General seeded mixture from the amount partially fiber complete not mad seeds and less amount to spin valid fiber there is seeds separate at the expense of fiber to destruction road is being placed

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